

ALLOMORPHIC AND ISOMORPHIC PROPERTIES OF CAUSALITY IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES.

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Annotation

This article provides information about the similar and dissimilar features of reason-result or in other words, causality in English and Uzbek languages, which are unrelated languages, In it, the opinions expressed by various scientists on this topic are cited. Causality belongs to a specific category, but in some language systems, grammatically connected meaning, that is, not even lexical-semantic, is included in the grammatical category. For example, some languages have causality clauses or causality suffixes.

Key words

causality, allomorphic, isomorphic, cause, cause-effect.

Causality is expressed differently in different language systems. In recent years, our linguists have been studying causation in various fields, dividing it into morphological, semantic, analytical, and syntactic types. In modern linguistics, a number of scientific research works have been carried out on the topic of causation. For example, among the linguists in this regard are A. Meye [Meye 1938, 227], L. Tenyer [Tener 1988, 272], N.D. Arutyunova [Arutyunova 1985, 30], I.A. Melchuk [Melchuk 1998, 381], Y.Y. Kordi [Cordi 1988, 11] and others shared their thoughts and opinions. We can see that there are large monographic research works on this topic based on Turkic language materials.

An example of the cause-and-effect relationship can be found in the words of W. von Humboldt: “ If we look at the current state of politics, art, and science, we will see that a long chain of cause-and-effect relationships lies at the basis of their development over the centuries” began to arouse interest in linguists [Humboldt 2000, 47].

Causality belongs to a certain category, but in some language systems, grammatically connected meaning, that is, not even lexical-semantic, is included in the grammatical category. For example, some languages have causality clauses or whereas others are rich with suffixes expressing causality.

S. D. Kanselson considers the concept of causality and cause-effect as two separate concepts. According to him, causality is the interaction of two separate actions with awareness of the executor, and cause is any action related to something [Katsnelson 1972, 87].

The German linguist Tanensanf defines causality as a cause that brings about a change in the object after itself [Tanensanf 1964, 16].

According to the information given in the book "Russian Grammar" written by A.H. Vostokov, conjunctions are divided into eleven types, one of them is "Винословные или причину показывающие" calling them, and giving them examples of connectives such as *ибо, поелику, понеже, так как, потому что, для того что, зато что*, (because, as long as, why, for, because, therefore) [Vostokov 1831, 216- 219].

In addition, F.I. Buslayev in his work on Russian grammar also provides information about causative sentences. He stated that there is a relationship between cause and effect based on the combination of thoughts through the meaning of causality. These relationships are manifested in two forms:

1) if the effect is expressed first, and then the cause appears, it is a causal form. For example, let's pay attention to this sentence: Sciences are useful because they enlighten the mind (*Польза науке есть следстве того, что она просвещаютъ*). In this case, the usefulness of knowledge is a result of the sharpening of the mind. The causal relationship is expressed by connecting the subordinate clause to the dominant clause through conjunctions such as *because, why*. 2) if the cause is given first, and then the effect occurs, it is called the inferred form: Sciences enlighten the mind: therefore they are useful (*Науки просвещаютъ разумъ: потому она полезны*). Such sentences are connected with the help of concluding conjunctions such as *therefore, so, and so* [Buslaev 1896, 184].

In his book "О значении формъ русского глагола", N.P. Nekrasov reported that there are verbs expressing the meaning of reason and they can be called "words of reason". It is said that they are "*винословное*", i.e. they have the meaning of urging or forcing to perform some action. For example, take the verb "to build" ("*строить*"). Indeed, a house is not built by a person, but by carpenters, masons, etc. In other words, the home owner orders the builders. So, the verb "to build" means to force someone to build a house. Therefore, such verbs are called "*de verbus causalibus*" ("causal verbs") in the grammar of other languages.

In my opinion, such verbs can be taken into account in the sense of expanding the category of verb ratio in the Russian language. However, verbs such as "to drink" ("*пить*"), "to eat" ("*кормить*") cannot be included in this category.

Because concepts such as forced drinking or feeding are not logically correct [Nekrasov 1865, 42].

But in some Turkic languages, suffixes that form the accusative ratio of the verb are interpreted as word-forming affixes. For example, B.A. Musukov's doctoral dissertation entitled "Морфологическая деривация глаголов в карачаево-балкарском языке" (Morphological derivation of verbs in the Karachay-Balkar language) called "Проблема изучения глагола образования в тюркских языках" (The problem of learning verb formation in Turkish languages) In the first chapter named, it is stated that in Karachoy-Bolgortili, the accusative suffixes of verbs such as -t, -dir, -ar serve to create new words, and artificial verbs are formed through this, and the vocabulary of Karachoy-Bolgortili emphasizes the expansion. In addition, he also says that in the semantic structure of the verbs formed with these additions, the meaning of calling to action has lost its power, and he cites the following as examples: to know-"*знать*" - inform-"*сообщать*"; to grow-"*расти*" - to grow -"*выращивать*" [Musukov 2011,17].

The problem of cause-and-effect relationships is very broad and multifaceted. In the linguistic literature, there is another term that corresponds to this category - causality. This term is closely related to causation, like "reason", but causation is a broader category that reflects the whole spectrum of connections between events in reality and is realized through syntactic means in language. Causality is interpreted as conditionality - a complex interaction of conditions, goals, consequences, causes [Вежбицкая 1997, 88-90]. The semantics of the category of cause is very broad, because the meanings of cause, cause-effect, and purpose are interconnected in it. In general, the semantic meaning of causal constructions is not only based on the concept of "cause", but also as "induction" - from the perspective of a pragmatic approach.

So, we can see that the category of causality shows its allomorphic and isomorphic properties in different languages.

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